

Enabling Capacity Scaling in Metro Networks with Multi Band Sliceable Transceiver Architectures

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ABSTRACT

Innovative multi band (MB) sliceable bandwidth/bitrate variable transceivers (S-BVTs) are proposed for future adoption in next-generation optical networks towards targeting the expected capacity scaling driven by the increasing traffic demand and emergence of new 6G services and applications with stringent requirements. To provide enhanced bandwidth/capacity and energy efficiency to support the envisioned growing demand, the use of MB technology is proposed and experimentally assessed up to 75 km of standard single mode fiber (SSMF) considering programmable MB S-BVTs. We demonstrate an aggregated capacity of 132.2 Gb/s exploiting S+C-bands and scalability towards enabling multi-Tb/s transmission within the metro/aggregation network segment. The sliceability of the MB S-BVT is demonstrated considering joint MB transmission (S+C) up to 2-hops network path of 75 km and an additional span of 50 km of SSMF for the C-band contribution. Different configurations based on single side band (SSB) and double side band (DSB) modulation and amplification technologies have been evaluated according to the particular scenario and band of operation. Finally, the programmability of the presented MB transceiver is also assessed as a key capability to promote network automation and flexibility. On this regard, a software-defined networking (SDN) agent based on open data model, such as OpenConfig, is implemented and validated to suitably reconfigure the transceiver according to the network requirements/demand. Key operational transceiver mode capabilities and configuration constraints, for the agent's implementation, are identified towards supporting MB transmission within future optical networks.

Keywords: Sliceable bandwidth/bitrate variable transceiver (S-BVT), multi-band (MB) transmission, software-defined networking (SDN), programmable transceivers, orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM), adaptive loading.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the emergence of 6G applications and services characterized by stringent requirements, in terms of bandwidth/capacity and the increasing connected devices and traffic, the exploitation and research of new technologies and innovations to be adopted in future networks are crucial.^{1,2} Regarding technical requirements, according to,³ the flow capabilities from access nodes towards other nodes (especially regional nodes) in the aggregation metro segment are expected to increase to a maximum of 2 Tb/s in the medium term and up to 8 Tb/s in the long term. Regional and national nodes should effectively handle the aggregated traffic, which might reach up to 100 Tb/s in the long term, 10 Tb/s in the medium term, and a few Tb/s in the short term, based on the analysis generated from traffic study of.³ Hence, a new breed of transmission systems/subsystems and switching options should be considered to meet the diverse 6G specifications across the network and expected traffic demand. This includes the capability to reconfigure the network to enable multi-Tb/s transmission in flexible manner within the metro segment.^{4,5}

A key enabler technology for 6G networks is multi band (MB) transmission, which offers increased capacity per fiber by exploiting the S-, E-, O- and U-bands in addition to C- and/or C+L-bands. MB is very attractive for achieving the required network capacity scaling, as it also maximizes the use of the currently deployed network infrastructure, resulting in a reduced capital expenditure.⁶ This will translate to an extended available bandwidth of of 51.88 THz accelerating the scalability and adaptability of optical networks in response to evolving demands.⁷ On the other hand, the diversity in performance characteristics across different frequency bands provides a strategic advantage as transmission can be flexibly adapted to the specific user needs. The allocation of specific applications and services can be allocated to optical bands that align with their unique

requirements. Hence, by tailoring the transmission to the characteristics of each band, multiband technology optimizes performance and responsiveness for a wide array of network applications.

However, MB transmission also introduces new challenges such as nonlinear effects (i.e. stimulated Raman scattering, SRS) that must be taken into account within the system design. Specifically, a power transfer between wavelengths with specific spacing occurs as a result of the interplay of wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) channels across the various bands.^{8,9} The maximum interaction/effect will be seen at 100 nm spacing. Finally, the most appropriate technology should be selected/considered for each network element according to the utilized band. For example, different optical amplifiers, filters, modulators, detectors and lasers should be included according to the operating band.¹⁰ Regarding amplification, praseodymium doped fiber amplifier (PDFA), neodymium DFA (NDFA), thulium DFA (TDFA) and erbium DFA (EDFA) could be considered for the O-band, E-band, S-band and C+L-bands, respectively.⁹ Alternative solutions based on bismuth DFA, Raman amplifiers, or semiconductor optical amplifiers (SOA) are also gaining special attention due to its lower cost.¹¹ In fact, Raman amplification has been demonstrated to be a flexible solution that offers an ultra-wide gain profile enabling operation across a wide range of wavelengths.¹² However, in general, adopting technologies tailored for specific bands beyond the traditional C-band are often accompanied by higher implementation costs.¹³ Thus, the most appropriate solution balancing cost and performance should be analyzed to ensure return on investment and long-term sustainability. Finally, new modular and scalable transceiver architectures capable to efficiently support MB operation are needed to be adopted in future 6G networks.

To this extent, sliceable bandwidth/bitrate variable transceivers (S-BVTs) arise as a transmission option to support MB, point-to-point (PtP) and point-to-multipoint (PtMP) operations, while providing cost-effective implementations within the metro-aggregation network segment.^{5,14} We propose S-BVTs with a modular and scalable architecture based on a pay-as-you grow approach that can exploit multiple technology options such as direct modulation and external modulation with direct detection (DD) or coherent reception.^{5,15} This flexible combination of the S-BVT building blocks enables to support multi-Tb/s transmission over the network, as demonstrated in.¹⁶ A key element of the MB S-BVT is the MB optical aggregator/distributor that ideally consists of a programmable wavelength spectral switches (WSS), which can operate across multiple bands or either uses a combination of WSSs, each working at a certain band, together with combiners/splitters or other passive solutions. A more static and cheaper solution can be based on the adoption of passive optical filters, such as band pass filters (BPFs), at the expenses of loosing transceiver flexibility and scalability. Different configurations based on single side band (SSB) and double side band (DSB) modulation and amplification options are investigated for different use cases/scenarios and optical bands. Additionally, the proposed transceiver solution is fully programmable and reconfigurable by the adoption and implementation of a software defined networking (SDN) agent based on OpenConfig data model.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the MB S-BVT architecture based on adaptive modulation and SDN capabilities towards enhancing overall network flexibility and adaptability. Section 3 shows the experimental setup to assess a proof of concept of the proposed MB S-BVT (C+S). Different configuration and technology options for a MB metro network scenario, considering different spans of SSMF up to 125 km and a MB node prototype have been analyzed. Additionally, the section shows the achieved experimental results after demonstrating the transmission of the proposed MB S-BVT over different paths of a MB metro network, as well as the SDN assessment results. Finally, conclusions are reported in section 4.

2. MB S-BVT ARCHITECTURE AND SDN CAPABILITIES

2.1 MB S-BVT

The proposed MB S-BVT has a modular and scalable architecture that enables unique flexibility and adaptability by providing the capability to create different slices and adjust bit rates dynamically according to specific requirements of distinct applications/users. This allows an efficient use of the available bandwidth and a better management of the network resources. As it can be seen in Fig. 1, the proposed transceiver scalable solution is based on a pay-as-you grow approach that contributes to a network infrastructure that aligns seamlessly with evolving demands and network needs while optimizing costs and enhancing performance. The modular design of the transceiver architecture allows for the easy integration of new functionalities and technologies, such as

Figure 1. MB S-BVT modular and scalable architecture.

MB, ensuring adaptability to emerging network requirements. This modularity facilitates the incorporation of advancements without overhauling the entire system, promoting a sustainable and future-proof network. The proposed architecture of the transceiver is depicted in Fig. 1. From the figure, it can be seen that the MB S-BVT is composed of multiple building blocks mainly bandwidth/bitrate variable transceivers (BVTs) that create different signals working at different wavelengths or even spectral bands (i.e. O-, E-, S-, C-, L- and U-bands). Hence, MB connectivity can be enabled further enhancing overall network efficiency by increasing the available bandwidth/resources, which can be assigned on demand according to the network needs. Each transmitter BVT (BVTx) consists of an adaptive digital signal processing (DSP) block, digital-to-analog conversion stage and an optical front-end that can be based on different technology such as direct modulation (i.e. using vertical cavity surface emitting lasers, VCSELs) and/or external modulation (i.e. using tuneable laser source, TLS and Mach Zehnder modulator, MZM) trading off complexity/cost versus performance.^{5,16} At the BVTx DSP block, orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) is performed to increase the system flexibility enabling an efficient use of the available bandwidth.⁵ Within the BVTx DSP block, data parallelization and mapping, training symbol (TS) insertion, inverse fast Fourier transform implementation, cyclic prefix (CP) insertion, serialization and radio frequency (RF) up-conversion processes are performed. On the other hand, bit and power loading (BPL) algorithms are implemented to maximize the capacity or the performance, adjusting the transmission parameters to match the channel conditions and the available bandwidth. The different signals are aggregated with an optical aggregator to create a high capacity data flow, which is sent to the network. This data flow can be disaggregated in different network nodes and distributed to particular destinations. The received flow is disaggregated and distributed by an optical distributor device to the different bandwidth/bitrate variable receivers (BVRxs). The optical aggregator/distributor device can be based on different technology capable to support MB operation trading of cost versus performance and programmability. In particular, static/non-reconfigurable BPFs can be used to aggregate and distribute the MB contributions. Programmable filters, such as WSSes, capable to work within different bands are also an attractive option that can enhance performance and resource efficiency.¹⁷ Additionally, programmable filters can also be used to implement SSB modulation in order to enhance resilience against chromatic dispersion. Each BVRx can also be based on different implementations (such as DD or coherent detection) tailored to specific network needs and requirements. At the receiver DSP

block, the corresponding OFDM signal is demodulated. Specifically, RF down-conversion, data parallelization, CP removal, fast Fourier transform implementation, equalization, symbol demapping and serialization processes are performed. The proposed MB S-BVT enables both PtP and PtMP connectivity further enhancing versatility and being able to facilitate efficient communication between a single source and multiple destinations. A single transceiver is capable to generate multiple slices that can be transmitted to multiple network end-points by means of optical switches and filters. This centralized model will reduce the number of active components and result in significant reductions in energy consumption and equipment costs. Finally, considering open an disaggregated transceiver approaches will enable individual optimization and upgrades of different network components, leading to a more efficient utilization of both power and bandwidth resources. The modular nature of this solution allows for targeted enhancements, ensuring that network infrastructure evolves in tandem with technological advancements.

2.2 MB S-BVT OPENCONFIG SDN AGENT

The SDN paradigm arises as a powerful tool to provide a dynamic network adaptability and configuration to the changing traffic demands, while optimizing the overall network performance.¹⁸ The integration of SDN with the proposed MB S-BVT will enable to suitably reconfigure the transceiver according to the traffic demand and network requirements maximizing efficiency and resource utilization.⁵ Network resources can be optimally utilized based on specific requirements of the MB S-BVT and the overall network, dynamically configuring optical channels and adjusting parameters. In particular, different programmable parameters and elements of the proposed MB S-BVT can be configured by SDN control plane by means of an SDN agent according to the network condition.¹⁹ For example, this can include the configuration of the power and central wavelength of the tuneable laser sources and DAC/ADC channels conforming each BVT/building block of the MB S-BVT. Additionally, SDN can enable end-to-end network visibility and retrieve detailed configuration information of the transceivers and network elements offering a comprehensive view of the network. This visibility facilitates to efficiently take decisions and manage troubleshoot issues, while planning network upgrade or optimization based on a holistic understanding of the network's capabilities. Having a centralized SDN control and orchestration will enhance the overall coherence and coordination of network operations while reducing complexity and costs.²⁰

In a disaggregated scenario, where multiple network elements can be from different providers and manufacturers the adoption of open standards and APIs is crucial to foster interoperability between different vendors' equipment.²¹ This reduces vendor lock-in, encourages innovation, and allows to adopt the best solutions to cover specific needs. In this context, the OpenConfig open data model is gaining special attention as a collaborative effort to develop vendor-neutral, programmable network device interfaces using open standards.²² One key advantage of the OpenConfig data model is that it allows network operators to manage transceivers from multiple vendors and platforms using a single, standardized interface. This simplifies the management of large, complex optical networks including a mix of equipment from different vendors. Another advantage of the OpenConfig data model is that it is designed to be easily extensible, to add new attributes (transceiver features) as needed to the model.

The OpenConfig data model comprises different abstract modules, with specific capabilities and features of a network device. In this work, relevant abstract modules for packet and optical SDN operations, particularly the Platform and Optical transport modules have been considered for the implementation of the SDN agents. The latter encompasses the model definition of the MB S-BVT, crucial for the SDN controller to conduct optical planning and validate end-to-end transmission impairments. Initially, the SDN controller retrieves a component list from the OpenConfig platform model, focusing on the operational mode datastore, and enumerates supported operational modes by the MB S-BVT. This facilitates comprehension of the device's structure, interfaces, configuration, and supported features. Extracted details from the operational mode datastore encompass the current operational state and configurations of the MB S-BVT, including transceiver characteristics and relevant parameters for physical impairment validation. Upon device discovery, the SDN controller leverages operational datastore information to configure optical channels, involving different source/destination MB S-BVTs. This configuration unfolds in two operations, encompassing (i) optical channel setup with parameters like central frequency, target output power, and operational mode, and (ii) logical channel assignment between a client port and a line port. The first operation (i) configures an optical channel with a particular power, central frequency and operational mode, while the second operation (ii) assigns a client port to an optical channel to establish a

connection between two transceivers. The operational mode field is vendor-specific and can include transceiver features, encoded in a single integer value. The OpenConfig SDN agent will use NETCONF/YANG and implement a subset of the OpenConfig data models with some extensions to include details about the transceiver operational modes. For the proposed MB S-BVT, according to operational mode extensions of the OpenConfig model for physical layer characterization, operational mode capabilities and configuration constraints have been identified in tables 1 and 2, respectively. A uniform loading is considered for the transceiver parameters extrac-

Table 1. MB S-BVT operational mode capabilities for physical layer characterization

Parameter	Value
Modulation format	MODULATION-FORMAT-QPSK
Bit-rate	TRIB-RATE-40G
Baud-rate	20GBd QPSK
Optical-channel-spectrum-width	50 GHz
Min-tx-OSNR	>40 dB
Min-rx-OSNR	33 dB
Min-input-power	0 dBm
Max-input-power	9 dBm
Max-chromatic-dispersion	2000 ps/nm
Max-differential-group-delay	1 ps
Max-polarization-dependent-loss	0.12 dB

Table 2. MB S-BVT configuration constraints for physical layer characterization

Parameter	Value
Min-central-frequency	191675803.99 MHz in C-band
Max-central frequency	205281058.6 MHz in S-band
Grid-type	FLEX
Adjustment-granularity	G-50GHz
Min-channel-spacing	50 GHz
Min-output-power	0 dBm
Max-output-power	25 dBm

tion and for the physical impairment transceiver capabilities modelling, C-band PtP transmission over 100 km has been taken into account.²³

3. EXPERIMENTAL ASSESSMENT

Here, an experimental setup for the proof of concept assessment of the proposed MB S-BVT considering different slices working at C- and S-bands is presented, as shown in Fig. 2. The BVTx is based on external modulation and includes a TLS, working on either C-band (1550.12nm) or S-bands (1500 nm), a MZM and a digital-to-analog converter (DAC) at 64 GSa/s. Regarding, the optical aggregator device is based on programmable filters to perform SSB modulation and a BPF to create a high capacity flow. A programmable WSS and a tuneable filter (TF) are used to suitably perform SSB modulation at the C-band (S_C) and S-band (S_{SSB}), respectively. DSB modulation has also been considered for the S-band slice (S_{DSB}) by only including the BPF and transmitting the DSB spectrum. The received MB flow is distributed with a BPF. At each BVRx, DD is performed by suitably using a simple photodetector (PIN) and analog-to-digital converter (ADC) working at 100 GSa/s. Additionally, each Rx front-end includes optical amplification and filtering stages, which are based on different technology options according to the spectral band of interest. For example, an EDFA amplifier is used for the C-band contribution and both SOA and TDFA have been evaluated for the S-band slice. For the filtering stage a WSS and a WDM filter are included for C- and S-band signals, respectively. A hard-decision forward error correction (HD-FEC) threshold of 7% overhead is fixed corresponding to a target BER of $4.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$. Figure 2, also details the main building blocks/elements of the OpenConfig agent that can be configured to program the proposed MB S-BVT.

Figure 2. MB S-BVT setup over a MB network. The additional emulated MB S-BVTs are indicated to assess the different scenarios.

Different target scenarios have been identified to evaluate sliceability/scalability over a MB network, as summarized in table 3. Multiple spans of standard single mode fiber (SSMF) up to 125 km have been considered targeting a metro/aggregation segment. A MB node based on a 16x16 polymer switch photonic integrated circuit (PIC) prototype,²⁴ which can also support spatial granularities, a SOA and a BPF is considered to emulate the transmission over a MB network, as also depicted in Fig. 2.¹⁹ In the figure, the MB node is depicted twice to emulate a 2-hops network scenario. However, for the experimental assessment 2 different inputs/outputs of the 16x16 switch have been used.

3.1 THE MB S-BVT PROOF OF CONCEPT ASSESSMENT

Table 3. Experimental assessment over different MB metro network scenarios at HD-FEC

Scenario	Bands	Rate (S_C ; S_{SDSB} ; S_{SSSB}) [Gb/s]	# hops	Length [km]	Path
1	C+S	66.5; 65; 65.7	0	0	B2B
2	C+S	48; 42; 42.5	1	25	SBVT-SBVT1
3	C+S	40; 26.5; 34	1	50	SBVT-SBVT1
4	C+S	29.3; 15.5; 24.6	2	75	SBVT-SBVT2 and SBVT3
5	C	20 (S_C)	3	125	SBVT-SBVT4

The achieved results in terms of capacity/reach are included in table 3. Maximum capacities per slice/band of 66.5 Gb/s, 65 Gb/s and 65.7 Gb/s are achieved in scenario1 (back-to-back, B2B) ensuring the target BER for the SSB C-band and for the DSB and SSB S-band slices, respectively. The channel profile in terms of SNR per slice of the SSB C-band and DSB S-band contributions are depicted in Fig. 3, showing similar performance in B2B. Scenario 2, targets MB transmission over 1-hop 25 km path achieving capacities of 48 Gb/s (SSB C-band) and of about 42 Gb/s in the case of S-band considering either DSB modulation with SOA and SSB with TDFA amplification. At this fiber length, the effect of CD is still limited. The benefits of adopting SSB and TDFA technology for the S-band slice are highlighted in scenario 3 and 4, where a 7.5 Gb/s and 9.1 Gb/s capacity increase is obtained compared to DSB transmission and SOA amplification. In these cases, the C-band contribution achieves 40 Gb/s after 50 km of SSMF (scenario 3) and 29.3 Gb/s after 75 km of SSMF (scenario 4) at the target BER. From Fig. 3, it can be seen that the DSB S-band spectrum is more affected by CD, presenting SNR attenuation peaks in particular subcarriers/frequencies within the signal bandwidth after a 2-hops 75 km path.

Figure 3. SNR profiles of SSB C-band and DSB S-band contributions considering (a) scenario 1 (back-to-back, B2B) and (b) scenario 4 (2-hops path of 75 km).

Thanks to the implementation of BPL algorithms, CD effect can be overcome and DSB modulation can also be considered/implemented ensuring the target BER at the expense of lower data rate. Finally, in scenario 5, the C-band slice traverses an additional fiber span of 50 km achieving 20 Gb/s after a 3-hops path of 125 km, demonstrating transceiver sliceability.

The presented proof of concept shows the capabilities and benefits of adopting a MB S-BVT solution for the metro/aggregation segment as a way towards efficiently and flexibly providing the required capacity scaling expected in 6G MB networks. Thanks to the modular and scalable transceiver approach, additional building blocks/slices can be enabled working at different bands beyond the C-band, according to the network condition and requirements. 33.6 Tb/s transmission can be enabled with 160 C-band channels of 25 GHz (SSB) and 350 S-band channels of 25 GHz (SSB). 22.6 Tb/s and 18.3 Tb/s MB transmission is envisioned after 25 km and 50 km paths by enabling all the available C+S-band SSB channels.

3.2 SDN ASSESSMENT

The OpenConfig MB S-BVT agent is integrated with ONOS SDN controller, which is responsible for mapping the information about operational modes into its North Bound Interface (NBI) so that the transport API (TAPI) Network Orchestrator can consume and query it to offer connectivity between two different MB S-BVTs distributed into the network. There are three main actions to perform in order to configure the MB S-BVT, including: i) device discovery; ii) configuration of the optical channel and iii) operational mode extensions for physical layer characterization. In particular, the first operation, within the device discovery action, that the controller needs to perform over the MB S-BVT is to retrieve the list of components. This is performed with the get NETCONF message following the OpenConfig platform mode, which defines the hardware components of the network device. The obtained information allows to discover the generic details of the device such as device model, manufacturer, supported bitrate, tuneability range and operational modes supported by the device. After discovery of the details of the device, the SDN controller can execute the configuration of an optical channel to establish the transmission, by configuring the source and destination MB S-BVTs, as performed in our previous work.²⁵ The request of a new optical channel is received by the ONOS SDN controller on its NBI interfaces and it is typically submitted including a suggested path and frequency slot. The configuration process will include: i) the configuration of the optical channel by setting up the central frequency, target output power and operational mode (i.e. 193100, 1.0, 100), ii) the configuration of the logical channel mainly to enable the interface and iii) the configuration of the assignment between a client port and a line port.

Finally, in relation to the third action related to the operational mode extensions for physical layer characterization, we have defined a set of attributes and properties to extend the operational mode, detailed in section 2.2, such as clients can retrieve the specific physical layer information associated with a transmission mode. The

SDN assessment is focused in this particular part regarding the extension of the operational mode for physical layer characterization and impairment validation. The details of a given operational mode (i.e. defined as 100) can be requested by a client using standard NETCONF/Yang as depicted in Fig. 4. A total time of 323 ms has been measured to obtain the parameters of the given operational mode, which response is depicted in Fig. 5.

```

<get>
  <filter type="subtree">
    <operational-modes xmlns="http://example.net/yang/openconfig-terminal-device-properties" xmlns:oc-opt-term-prop-
types="http://example.net/yang/openconfig-terminal-device-property-types" xmlns:oc-opt-types="http://opencon-
fig.net/yang/transport-types">
      <mode-descriptor>
        <mode-id>100</mode-id>
      </mode-descriptor>
    </operational-modes>
  </filter>
</get>

```

Figure 4. Request of 100 operational mode

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<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<rpc-reply xmlns="urn:ietf:params:xml:ns:netconf:base:1.0" message-id="1">
  <data>
    <operational-modes xmlns="http://example.net/yang/openconfig-terminal-device-properties">
      <mode-descriptor>
        <mode-id xmlns:oc-opt-term-prop-types="http://example.net/yang/openconfig-terminal-device-property-types" xmlns:oc-opt-
<state>
          <mode-id>100</mode-id>
          <mode-type xmlns:oc-opt-term-prop-types="http://example.net/yang/openconfig-terminal-device-property-types">oc-opt-te
</state>
        <explicit-mode>
          <operational-mode-capabilities>
            <state>
              <modulation-format>oc-opt-term-prop-types:MODULATION_FORMAT_QPSK</modulation-format>
              <bit-rate xmlns:oc-opt-types="http://openconfig.net/yang/transport-types">oc-opt-types:TRIB_RATE_40G</bit-rate>
              <baud-rate>2000000000.0</baud-rate>
              <optical-channel-spectrum-width>50.0</optical-channel-spectrum-width>
              <min-tx-osnr>40.0</min-tx-osnr>
              <min-rx-osnr>33.0</min-rx-osnr>
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              <max-input-power>9.0</max-input-power>
              <max-chromatic-dispersion>200.0</max-chromatic-dispersion>
              <max-differential-group-delay>1.0</max-differential-group-delay>
              <max-polarization-dependent-loss>0.12</max-polarization-dependent-loss>
            </state>
          <fec>
            <state>
              <fec-coding>oc-opt-term-prop-types:FEC_HD</fec-coding>
              <coding-overhead>7.0</coding-overhead>
              <coding-gain>8.53</coding-gain>
              <pre-fec-ber-threshold>0.00000000001</pre-fec-ber-threshold>
            </state>
          </fec>
          <penalties>
            <penalty>
              <parameter-and-unit xmlns:oc-opt-term-prop-types="http://example.net/yang/openconfig-terminal-device-property-t
              <up-to-boundary>800.0</up-to-boundary>
              <state>
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                <up-to-boundary>800.0</up-to-boundary>
                <penalty-value>10.0</penalty-value>
              </state>
            </penalty>
          </penalty>
        </operational-mode-capabilities>
      </explicit-mode>
    </operational-modes>
  </data>
</rpc-reply>

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Figure 5. Reply of the Openconfig terminal device

4. CONCLUSIONS

A modular MB S-BVT is proposed as a key transceiver solution to meet the capacity scaling requirements of the incoming 6G networks while offering unique capabilities. Specifically, a proof of concept of the proposed solution is experimentally validated, considering different target scenarios and transceiver configurations. The programmable and scalable transceiver enables the reconfiguration of the transmission, providing efficient bandwidth allocation and MB, PtP and PtmP operation through the network. A maximum capacity of 130 Gb/s is assessed, enabling 2 slices in the C+S bands, supporting scalability towards achieving multi-Tb/s transmission. SSB and DSB transmission with different amplification technology, according to the band of operation, have been evaluated to analyze the most appropriate solution for each use case/scenario. Enhanced performance is obtained by considering SSB and TDFA S-band amplification after 50 km and 2-hops path of 75 km. The C-band slice performance has been evaluated up to 3-hops path of 125 km, demonstrating 20 Gb/s and transceiver sliceability at the target BER. Finally, an OpenConfig SDN agent is implemented to dynamically reconfigure the MB S-BVT identifying key operational mode capabilities and configuration constraints to further support the requirements and programmability of future 6G optical networks. A total time of 323 ms has been measured to retrieve the transceiver parameters of a particular operational mode, considering model extensions for physical layer characterization.

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